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Integration of Wannier Function-Based Transport Data into the NOMAD Repository

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Abstract

Wannier functions are widely used for the calculations of a wide range of physical properties, enabling data-driven materials design. In particular, transport property calculations based on the Wannier functions are typically multi-step processes, including self-consistent density functional theory (DFT), Wannierization, and Wannier interpolation, requiring the use of multiple software packages. In this work, we take spin Hall conductivity (SHC) as an example, where maximally localized Wannier functions generated using the Wannier90 package [1] are employed. The so-obtained data from high-throughput (HTP) DFT calculations is parsed using plugins from NOMAD [2], with an extension to evaluate the Wannier-based band structures from the hopping matrix elements. Furthermore, organizing everything into a workflow, WannierBerri [3] is used for the calculation of SHC, with a corresponding plugin developed within the NOMAD framework for parsing Wannier Berri SHC output files. Our dataset currently contains approximately 5000 sets of Wannier-based transport calculations.

Keywords: Wannier Functions, spintronics, NOMAD, spin Hall conductivity

Resources

Extended Wannier90 parser in NOMAD and WannierBerri spin Hall conductivity parser.

- Updated Wannier90 parser. <https://github.com/16-vikrant/electronic-parsers/tree/develop/electronicparsers/wannier90>
- Wannier Berri parser. <https://github.com/16-vikrant/nomad-parser-wannierberri>

Author contributions

Vikrant Chaudhary: Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Software, and Visualization

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Stefan Blügel: Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition, and Project administration

Hongbin Zhang: Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition, and Project administration

Competing interests

"The authors declare that they have no competing interests."

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